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Effect of Audio-Visual Materials on Students' Interest and Achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of audio-visual (AV) materials on students' interest and achievement in Basic Science and Technology (BST) in Benue State, Nigeria. The study answered two research questions and tested two null hypotheses. A quasi-experimental of non-randomized, pretest posttest control group design was adopted. Two instruments, Basic Science and Technology Interest Scale (BSTIS) and Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test (BSTAT) were validated and used for data collection. Reliability coefficients of BSTIS and BSTAT were established at 0.79 and 0.76 using Cronbach-Alpha Method and Kuder-Richardson-20 formula respectively. The sample size of 127 Upper Basic III students was drawn from the population of 14,894 using multi-stage sampling technique. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering research questions while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

The result revealed a significant difference between the mean interest and achievement scores of students taught BST using AV materials and those taught without the use of AV materials with large effect sizes of $\eta_p^2 = 0.76$ and $\eta_p^2 = 0.81$ respectively. Based on these findings, it was concluded that the use AV materials is an effective approach in teaching Basic Science and Technology, because the approach enhanced students' interest and achievement of BST concepts. It was recommended among others that AV materials should be used for the teaching of BST in particular and other science subjects in general where necessary; that stakeholders in education should organize seminars and conferences to train BST teachers on the use of AV materials for teaching in order to enhance students' interest and achievement in Science.

Keywords: Audio-Visual Materials, Interest, Achievement, Basic Science and Technology, Basic Education

Introduction

Basic Science and Technology can be seen as the foundation for the development of scientific and technological knowledge and skills, which are viable tools for the socio-economic development of any nation. Among the objectives of Basic Science and Technology are to develop and sustain students' interest and increase their achievement in science and technology since today's society depends largely on development in science and technology (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2013)

The teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology plays a pivotal role in shaping the future and well-being of any nation. The relevance of Basic Science and Technology for providing a strong solid foundation in science and technology has drawn the attention of the world all over today to turn toward its development and sustainability. This is because every proper function of life depends greatly on good foundation in science and technology. This implies that all developing nations, Nigeria inclusive, are struggling hard to have a good solid foundation in science and technology through the proper teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology so they could achieve a significant attainment in scientific and technological advancement. Education in science and technology is focused on helping man to gain a deeper knowledge and understanding of the working of the natural environment (Oladejo & Gbolagade, 2011). It would not have been possible for man to explore the universe if it is not for the help and the application of scientific and technological knowledge and skills. This implies that for any nation aspiring to attain desirable development in science and technology, more emphasis must be placed on the effective teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology at the basic educational level to provide students with a good solid foundation in scientific and technological knowledge (Upu & Okwara, 2024).

Basic Science and Technology is the fundamental subject for providing holistic scientific and technological knowledge and skills to the students at the basic education level. Basic Science and Technology is the form of science and technology that is offered at the 9-year Basic Educational Programme of Nigeria which involved concepts that cut across Chemistry, Physics and Biology. It prepares students at the Basic level of educational system for subsequent studies in specialized core science and technology related field (Francis, 2017). The goals of teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology have not been

achieved over the years as evident in the poor achievement of students in the subject over the years.

The poor interest and achievement of students in Basic Science and Technology has been attributed to different reasons, among which is the teaching method that has been considered to be the most significant factor. This means that understanding Basic Science and Technology concepts will not be completely accomplished without the assistance of teaching intervention like the use of audio-visual materials. Ibe and Abamu (2018) assert that the teaching and learning of any science subject that is not supported by audio-visual materials will most likely lead to students being passive listeners which will result to poor interest and achievement. Ojelade *et al.* (2020) supported this assertion with their findings which revealed that audio-visual materials have significant impact on students' interest and achievement in the teaching and learning of science. Rasul and Priya (2018) also revealed that students that were exposed to audio-visual materials during classroom lessons achieved higher test scores than the group that were not exposed to audio-visual materials.

Audio-visual materials are referred to as multi-sensory interactive applications or presentations that make use of a variety of digital media to communicate messages, ideas or information to an audience, including text, pictures, sound, and videos (Eraikhuemen & Enogie 2017). As a result, when words are supplemented by pictures and animations, ideas are simpler to convey and understood better by providing new level of learning experiences to the learner (Tang & Daniel, 2017; Agada, 2021).

Advancement in technology is the variable tool for teaching and learning, that allowed students to go beyond the traditional classroom setting of talk and chalk approach. Educational audio-visual materials when properly use for teaching and learning enhance students' interest, achievement and retention (Tairu *et al.*, 2018).

Students' interest can be described as persistent tendency to pay attention and enjoy some activities or contents. Abakpa (2011) asserts that interest is an energized power of learning, without which meaningful learning cannot take place. Ugwuanyi (2015) observed that the type of interest students bring into the classroom is the reflection of their academic achievement and retention. The implication is that if students have a positive interest towards BST, they will not only enjoy studying it but would also derive satisfaction from the knowledge and skills acquired to improve their achievement and retention.

Achievement is an exhibition of knowledge attained, or skills developed by students in a subject as determined by test scores assigned by the teachers. Upu and Adzape (2024) conceptualized students' achievement as their ability to provide evidence of the attainment of certain levels of classroom instructions and learning experiences. The achievement of students in Basic Science and Technology is central for the production of scientific and technological manpower for national development.

Statement of Problem

Basic Science and Technology is a very important subject, not only as a pre-requisite subject for career development in science and technology but also as foundation for national development. This is because Basic Science and Technology serves as a springboard for many

careers in science and technology and has applications nearly in every facet of life. Despite the importance of Basic Science and Technology for national development, the persistent poor achievement of students in the subject year in year out in the past one decade has been a matter of serious concern to educationists, researchers and stakeholders in education. This necessitates the present study to determine how the use of audio-visual material will influence students' interest and academic achievement in Basic Science and Technology.

Research Objectives

The objective of the study is to examine the effect of audiovisual materials on students' interest and academic achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study is to examine:

- i. The effect of audio-visual materials on students' interest in Basic Science and Technology in Benue State, Nigeria.
- ii. The effect of audio-visual materials on students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught BST with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method?
- ii. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was a quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the researchers used a non-randomized pretest post-test intact class control group design. This design was used because it was not possible for the researchers to have a complete randomization of the subjects as this would have disrupted the normal classroom organization of the schools. The population of this study was 14,894 Upper Basic III students (UB III) in the 2023/2024 academic session. This population is drawn from 83 schools that have been teaching Basic Science and Technology for over a decade. The sample of this study was 127 Upper Basic III students drawn from four schools. Multi-stage sampling technique was used for selecting the sample. Instruments used for this study were

Basic Science and Technology Interest Scale (BSTIS) and Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test (BSTAT). The research instruments were validated by three experts. The reliability of BSTIS and BSTAT were calculated using Cronbach Coefficient Alpha test method and Ruder-Richardson formula 20 (KR-20) which gave the values of 0.79 and 0.76 respectively. These values show that instruments are both internally consistent and reliable. Basic Science and Technology teachers currently teaching in the sampled schools were used for the study in both experimental and control groups as research assistants. BSTIS and BSTAT were administered to students as pre-tests to ascertain their initial interest and initial level of their understanding of BST concepts before commencement of the treatment. The control group was also taught the same content without the use of audio-visual materials. The teaching lasted for six weeks with 12 periods both in experimental and control group. Immediately after the conclusion of the teaching, the BSTIS and BSTAT were given as post-test and scores were recorded. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). ANCOVA was used to check the initial difference that might exist between the groups due to the random assigning of the schools.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean interest ratings of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught BST with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method?

Table 1: Mean Interest Rating and Standard Deviation of students taught Basic Science and Technology with AV and those that taught without AV

Group	N	Pre-Interest		Post-Interest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental Group	75	2.03	1.08	3.86	1.04	1.83
Control Group	54	2.10	1.06	2.50	1.05	0.40
Total	129					
Mean Difference		-0.07		1.36		1.43

The findings in Table 1 showed that the mean pre-interest ratings for the students that were taught Basic Science and Technology using AV materials and those taught with conventional method was 2.03 and 2.10 with standard deviations of 1.08 and 1.06 respectively. However, the mean post-Interest ratings for the students that were taught BST with AV materials was 3.86 and the mean post-interest ratings for those taught with conventional method was 2.50, with standard deviations of 1.04 and 1.05 respectively. The mean gain between the two groups, however, was found to be 1.43. Research hypothesis 1 was tested in Table 2 to establish if this gain is significant.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance on Students' Mean Interest Ratings in BST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta Squared
Corrected Model	5067.567 ^a	2	2533.784	210.307	.000	.397	
Intercept	33979.036	1	33979.036	2820.305	.000	.415	
Pre-test	209.274	1	209.274	17.370	.002	.024	
Interest	413.408	1	413.408	12.814	.000	.76	
Error	7710.694	239	32.262				
Total	1081300.000	243					
Corrected Total	12778.261	242					

a. R Squared = .397 (Adjusted R Squared = .393)

Findings in Table 2 indicated that F-value for interest was 12.814 at the significance value of 0.000, which is less than the p-value of 0.05. Based on this finding, hypothesis 2 which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students that were taught BST using AV material and those that were taught with conventional method, is rejected. This means that there is significant difference between the mean interest ratings of students that were taught BST using AV and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology with conventional method. To assess the effect size between the groups the computed value of *partial eta squared* gave the value of 0.76.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method?

Table 3: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of students taught Basic Science and Technology using AV and those taught without AV

Group	N	Pre-BSTAT		Post-BSTAT		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental Group	75	26.21	1.02	69.27	1.01	43.06
Control Group	54	26.31	1.04	54.65	1.02	28.34
Total	129					
Mean Difference		-0.10		14.62		14.72

Table 3 results showed that the mean pretest scores of students that were taught Basic Science and Technology using AV material was 26.21 with standard deviation of 1.02 while the mean pretest scores of those taught with conventional method was 26.31 with

standard deviation of 1.04. The posttest means scores for the students that were taught BST using AV material was 69.27 with a standard deviation of 1.01 and those that were taught with conventional method was 54.65 with standard deviation of 1.02 respectively. The mean gain difference between students that were taught BST using AV and those taught with CM was 14.72. This indicates that students that were taught BST with the use of AV materials achieved higher than those that were taught with CM. To determine if this difference is significant, hypothesis 2 was tested in Table 4.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students in Basic Science and Technology between those who are taught with audio-visual materials and those taught with the conventional method.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on Students' Achievement in BST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
corrected Model	9893.146 ^a	2	4946.673	328.617	.000	.340
Intercept	19239.312	1	19239.312	1,278.105	.000	.110
Pretest	28.652	1	28.652	1.903	.122	.041
Group	687.486	1	687.486	45.671	.003	.81
Error	3597.763	239	15.053			
Total	405400.000	243				
Corrected Total	4490.909	242				

a. R Squared = .199 (Adjusted R Squared = .190)

Findings in Table 4 revealed that the experimental group had F-value of 45.671 at the significance value of 0.003. This significance value is less than p-value of 0.05 (i.e. $p = 0.05 > 0.003$). With this result, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of students in BST between those that were taught BST with AV materials and those that were taught without CM was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of students that were taught Basic Science and Technology using AV and those taught without AV. The *partial eta squared* was investigated which gave a value of 0.81. This value indicated that there is a high effect size between the experimental and control group.

Discussion

The findings of the analysis showed that the mean post interest ratings of students that were taught BST using AV was 3.87, while those students taught with CM was 2.96 with a mean gain difference was 1.43. Therefore, the students that were taught BST using AV materials had higher mean interest ratings to Basic Science and Technology than their counterparts that were taught without AV. This result was further supported by testing hypothesis 1, which showed a significant difference between mean interest ratings of students in the experimental and control groups. This finding agrees with those of Ibe and Abamuche

(2019) and Agada (2021) whose results indicated that the students that were taught science subjects using AV materials had higher mean interest ratings to science than those that were taught without the use of AV. This means that audio-visual materials have the potential of instilling positive interests in the teaching and learning of science among students, particularly at the basic education level.

The results of the analysis showed that the mean post-test achievement scores of students that were taught Basic Science and Technology using AV was 69.27 and those that were taught with CM was 54.65 with the mean difference of 14.72. These results indicated that students that were taught BST using AV materials achieved higher results than those that were taught with CM. This result was further tested for significance by testing hypothesis 2 which shows a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The findings of this study agree with those of Tairu *et al.* (2018) and Ojelade *et al.* (2020) who revealed that students taught the concepts of science with AV materials had higher mean achievement scores than those that were taught without the use of AV. The authors argued that the higher achievement of students that were taught science concepts with AV was because the approach was able to integrate and facilitate meaningful learning of scientific concepts by the students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, this study concluded that the use audio-virtual materials for teaching and learning Basic Science and Technology concepts is an effective approach, because it facilitated the improvement of students' interest and achievement in Basic Science and Technology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The use of audio-visual materials is an effective approach in teaching and learning; therefore, it should be used by Basic Science and Technology teachers for the teaching of relevant concepts in order to improve students' interest and achievement where applicable.
- ii. Science educators should endeavour to incorporate AV skills in the training of prospective Basic Science and Technology teachers so that they can use it for teaching when they finally enter the teaching profession.
- iii. The Federal and State Ministries of Education should organize in-service training programmes in the form of conferences, seminars and workshops for serving Basic Science and Technology teachers to acquaint them with appropriate knowledge and skills on how to use audio-virtual materials for effective teaching of science and technology particularly at basic levels of education.
- iv. The government at all levels and schools' administrators should endeavour to provide adequate facilities and environment to incorporate the use of audio-virtual materials for effective teaching of Basic Science and Technology.

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